

Assessing the Interest and Skill based Career Choice among the Higher Secondary Students in Coimbatore

¹Ms.P.Selvapranambika, ²Prof.A.Vimala

¹Research scholar (Ph.D- FT), ²Head of the Department- Guide
Department of Extension and Career Guidance
Bharathiar University

Abstract: Interest and skills place major element in career growth of students and it is a lifelong process. Skill explains about the learned ability to become an expertise in one field, career interest explains about the preference and interest about the student choice of career. Systematic career guidance can be given to the student after assessing the interest and skills for their better career decision. The current research aims at finding the interest and skills of the students and their career selection pattern. *Methodology:* This study is a descriptive and exploratory in nature and includes oral interview method and questionnaire as tools for data collection. *Findings:* From the findings and discussion, the major result found that 84.3% of them were not received any career guidance in school level, 60.4% of the students stated that they want to select their career based on their Interest and skills, 90% of them were opined they are in need of career guidance in the school level. The major implication of the research is, every school has to offer early career guidance to the students for their better understanding before the selection of course.

Keywords: Students interest, skills, career choice and career guidance

I. INTRODUCTION

Interest and skill place major element in career growth of students and it is a lifelong process, Self-assessment is necessary to understand one's capabilities and drawbacks. The various career opportunities should be explored in details to find a fit between one's abilities and the opportunities provided by a career option. A good career planning helps a person grow in life in their professional career, which also help them grow personally. The right career choice for the students entering into the professional education is critical having high impact on their professional life and future achievement. A miss-perceived career choice directs all individual efforts and resources into wrong direction, when not aligned with the expectations; would not only be frustrating rather draining of the individual energy and wastage of resources.

According to UNICEF (2019) only 47 percent of Indian graduates by 2030 will have the basic skills to be employable. It also mentioned low quality of education and suboptimal vocational training which do not give students the desired skill levels which was demanded by the labour which is identified as major skill gap. The skill

gap plays major element between the education and labour market. Also the study stated that many of the graduates selected their career based on the parents, friends and teachers influence rather than their interest.

II. LITERATURE SUPPORT

Clement H (2014) investigated one of the major factors is the mismatch of personality with a course/career. In the process of making career choices, personality plays a significant role; productivity, fulfillment and motivation are directly related to the individual. Lack of fit can be the most dangerous cause of dissatisfaction and ends up in to the stress career failure.

Rebecca J. et al (2016) conducted a study on 399 students in Kenya which resulted in that there is a relationship between skills, interest and personality types, and career choice. Most of the students were satisfied with the course they selected before entering the university which indicates that suitable career choice for students would improve satisfaction and success in their course of study and future employment.

Running head: INTEREST FIT AND JOB SATISFACTION Interest Fit and Job Satisfaction: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Kevin A. Hoff

Kevin Hoff et.al (2020) although the report suggested that interest fits predict job satisfactions, interest fit is more strongly related to performance outcomes and satisfaction on overall career path. The study concludes by presenting a series of recommendations for improving the use of interest assessments in career and organizational settings

Running head: INTEREST FIT AND JOB SATISFACTION Interest Fit and Job Satisfaction: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Kevin A. Hoff

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is a descriptive and random sampling method was adopted for the selection of respondents. The research was carried out among the students of higher secondary in

private and government schools in Coimbatore. A structured questionnaire was administered among the sample respondent of 127 students to know their nature of career choice and factors influencing for career selection. The secondary data were collected from the various journals, articles, newspapers, books, and websites for the support of selection of variables and to understand and the earlier researcher view on career selection based on the skills and interest.

IV. OBJECTIVES

The research focuses on the following objectives to understand the higher secondary students career choice

- To assess the demographic profile among the students of higher secondary school
- To understand the factors affecting career choice among the students of higher secondary school
- To assess the skill and interest-based selection of career among the higher secondary school
- To find the knowledge on career information among selected respondents.

4.1 Findings of the research

The collected data has been tabulated and analysed by applying necessary statistical tools to arrive the result for the framed objectives. The findings are listed below.

4.2 Respondent's biographical details found

54.2% of them were female among the total respondents, 75% of the government school respondent parents were going for daily wages, 43.3% of parents were doing business among the respondents of private school, 46.4% of parents were 10th qualified and same represented as illiterate in the government school.

4.3 Career Interest of Higher Secondary school students

39.75% of students interested to take any Arts and Science field who is studying at government and Private school, 45.1 % of students were opined that the financial crisis is the most important factors for selecting the desired career.

4.4 Career choice based on interest and skill

72.4% of the students were opined that they were not identified their skills and abilities and 61.8% of the students opined that no one is helping to identify their skills. 78.2% of the students stated that they were not familiar about the career growth of the next level courses. 84.3% of the respondents reveals that they did not get any career related event in the school level. 60.4% of the students stated that they want to select their career based on their interest and skills. 90% of them were opined that they are in need of career guidance in the school level.

4.5 Subject wise skill analysis

On an average 68.3 % from government and private school students reported they have reading and writing skill in English, on an average 58.4 % from both government and private school students reported they can do Mathematics in moderate level, on an average 45.6% from both government and private school students reported that they can do logical and aptitude test. On an average 66.2% were reported that they are good at Tamil language. The above is the observed skill from the respondent's opinion and are not test with questions.

V. CAREER KNOWLEDGE AMONG SCHOOL STUDENTS

Only 22.8 % of the students mentioned that they have the knowledge and application procedure to select the college and course, 60% of students mentioned that they have decided their choice of course after the completion of 12th and based on the available course for their scored mark.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are arrived based on the findings and discussion. The result to be noted that 84.3% of them were not received any career guidance in school level and 60.4% of the students stated that they want to select their career, based on their interest and skills and 90% of them were opined they are in need of career guidance in the school level. It is recommended that

- Every school has to offer early career guidance to the students for their better understanding before the selection of course in higher education level and to understand the job opportunities too.
- The schools and colleges have to organize a career fair in the campus to make the students to understand their next level education, skills to be upgraded and procuring the eligibility. The above will make the students to be familiar on various courses and job opportunities for their next level career preparation.
- Capacity building program on career guidance to be offered for the faculty members/ placement officers to upgrade their knowledge on various to find the occupational and educational information to convey among their wards. Also teachers of the concerned discipline have to be familiar on assessment of skills and interest through testing and non testing techniques.

REFERENCES

- [1] [https://ibimapublishing.com/articles/JSAR/2017/718849/MiracleIfeomaMbagwuetal\(2016\).InfluenceofparentseducationalbackgroundoncareerchoiceofteenagersamongseniorsecondaryschoolstudentsinOwerri.EdoriumJournalofPsychology,Vol2,2016,14-20.](https://ibimapublishing.com/articles/JSAR/2017/718849/MiracleIfeomaMbagwuetal(2016).InfluenceofparentseducationalbackgroundoncareerchoiceofteenagersamongseniorsecondaryschoolstudentsinOwerri.EdoriumJournalofPsychology,Vol2,2016,14-20.)

- [2] <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1089785.pdf>
 [3] http://www.iaclp.org/yahoo_site_admin/assets/docs/6_Valles_IJCLP_11.238192305.pdf
 [4] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344755247_Interest_Fit_and_Job_Satisfaction_A_Systematic_Review_and_Meta-Analysis
 [5] <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/92-of-employees-believe-india-suffers-from-skills-gap-study/articleshow/78293159.cms>

Table 1:

S.No	Career Knowledge	Yes, I know %	No, I don't know %	Parents will decide %
1	Career decision after 12th	60	10	20
2	Admission Procedure/college details	22.8	58.2	20

Table 2:

S.No	Occupation	Parents occupation of Government school students	Parents occupation of private school
1	Daily Wages	75	10
2	Agriculture	23	35
3	Driver	2	6.7
4	Business	0	43.3
5	Govt Job	0	3
6	Teacher	0	2
TOTAL		100	100

Table 3:

S.No	Parents Education	Government School	Private School
1	Degree Holder	3.2	10.8
2	Up to 12th Standard	4	45.2
3	Up to 10th Standard	46.4	24.4
4	Not Studies	46.4	10

Table 4:

S.No	Career interest based on interest and skill	%
1	Students were not able to identified their skills and abilities	72.4
2	students opined that no one is helping to identify their skills.	61.8
3	Students were not familiar about the career growth of the next level courses	78.2
4	Students did not get any career related event in the school level	84.3
5	Students want to select their career based on their Interest and skills	60.4
6	Students are in need of career guidance in the school level.	90

Table 5:

Subject wise skill	Scoring %
English	68.3
Tamil	58.4
Logical and Aptitude	45.6
Maths	66.2

Table 6:

S.No	Career knowledge among school students	%
1	Students know the knowledge of procedure and details to select the college and course	22.8
2	Students mentioned that they have decided their choice of course after the completion of 12th.	60